

Of Frames and schema evolution - The newest features of podio

Placido Fernandez Declara¹, Frank Gaede², Gerardo Ganis¹,
Benedikt Hegner^{1*}, Clement Helsens³, Thomas Madlener^{2*}, Andre
Sailer¹, Graeme A Stewart¹ and Valentin Volk¹

¹CERN, Switzerland

²Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, Germany

³KIT, Germany

E-mail: benedikt.hegner@cern.ch, thomas.madlener@desy.de

Abstract. The podio event data model (EDM) toolkit provides an easy way to generate a performant implementation of an EDM from a high level description in yaml format. We present the most recent developments in podio, most importantly the inclusion of a schema evolution mechanism for generated EDMs as well as the “Frame”, a thread safe, generalized event data container. For the former we discuss some of the technical aspects in relation with supporting different I/O backends and leveraging potentially existing schema evolution mechanisms provided by them. Regarding the Frame we introduce the basic concept and highlight some of the functionality as well as important aspects of its implementation. The usage of podio for generating different EDMs for future collider projects (most importantly EDM4hep, the common EDM for the Key4hep project) has inspired new features. We present some of those smaller new features and end with a brief overview on current developments towards a first stable version as well as an outlook on future developments beyond that.

1. Introduction

podio is an event data model (EDM) toolkit that allows one to generate thread safe and efficient C++ code from a high level description in yaml format. It favors composition over inheritance and uses plain-old-data (POD) types wherever possible. EDMs generated by podio feature a User Layer consisting of thin handles offering value semantics, which is powered by two more layers that manage resources and relations between objects. This layered approach also allows one to support multiple I/O backends, where ROOT [1] is the default and an alternative based on *Simple Input/Output* (SIO) [2] is also available. For more details about how podio generates EDMs we refer to previous publications [3, 4, 5]. One of the main use cases for podio at the moment is the generation of EDM4hep [5, 6], the EDM of the Key4hep project [7, 8, 9, 10].

In these proceedings we discuss a few recent developments in the podio toolkit. One is the introduction of the *Frame* concept, where we introduce the basic ideas and some implementation details in Sec. 2. Another important recent development is related to schema evolution of generated EDMs. This has been a longstanding missing feature of podio, and we discuss the plans and currently existing functionality in Sec. 3. We also give brief descriptions of other, smaller recent developments in Sec. 4 before we conclude with a brief outlook.

2. The Frame concept and design

One of the shortcomings of podio so far was its usability in multi-threaded contexts. The *EventStore* that has been shipped with podio was never designed to support this, and has far outlived its original purpose of an example implementation for a transient event store. The *Frame* concept has been developed to address these shortcomings and to provide a more production ready way of accessing and operating on data. The main design goals for the Frame concept are

- Serve as a container that aggregates all relevant data
- Define an *interval of validity* or category for the contained data
- Easy to use and thread-safe interface for accessing and storing data
- Clearly defined ownership and mutability of data that is also reflected in the interface, while still supporting value semantics
- Separation of reading data and the necessary processing in order to, e.g. do schema evolution or establish inter-object relations

By keeping the Frame concept rather general and not prescribing any ad-hoc definition of its category or interval of validity, we aim at a more general concept than its potential main use case as a HEP event data container. Since the contained data and the user define the category of each individual Frame it should also be usable by experiments that have no clear notion of an “event”, but rather operate with, e.g., readout time frames.

The design choices for achieving a thread-safe interface and for clearly defining ownership of the contained data are closely related, and the former more or less necessitates the latter. The easiest way to make concurrent access to collections stored in a Frame possible is to ensure that these accesses are read-only and so, by definition, do not mutate stored data. In order to ensure that users cannot keep a mutable reference to collections they put into a Frame they have to explicitly relinquish ownership by *moving* collections into the Frame, as shown in Fig. 1. Although C++ does not have the notion of a destructive move it is possible to enforce this ownership transfer at compile time. One of the drawbacks of this approach is that it is still possible to use *moved-from* collections. Even though this does not touch the thread-safety properties of the Frame, the results might be confusing for non-experienced C++ users. Here we have to rely on tooling, extensive documentation and training of users to not use moved-from objects in C++.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the Frame concept and the ownership and mutability of collection data.

For the implementation of the Frame class we decided to use type erasure. This allows us to have a move-only type that still has value semantics. It is also required by the goal of

clearly decoupling I/O from the Frame interface, as it allows us to make Frames constructible from almost arbitrary *Frame data*. With this possibility each I/O backend can define its own implementation of such data that optimally uses its capabilities, as long as the provided implementation fulfills a rather minimal interface to actually access the POD buffers from which a collection can be constructed.

The basic assumptions for I/O in the Frame concept are that each file that is read from or written to is only operated on from a single thread. This assumption is exploited inside the Frame by assuming that no other thread has direct access to the Frame data from which it has been constructed, greatly simplifying the necessary synchronization. Another aspect that contributed to this decision is the much simpler implementation of basic readers and writers, which now exist for both available backends, ROOT and SIO. Here we see podio as a provider of basic building blocks that can be combined by downstream users in more complex scenarios, e.g. having one thread producing Frame data with a reader and several threads consuming these to construct Frames from.

All the basic functionality for the Frame concept is in place, and the main work for the near future is to replace all usages of the EventStore with Frame based I/O in the Key4hep stack. Another possibility in the current design is the implementation of policies that change the Frame behavior without changing its interface.

3. Schema evolution in podio

Since detector technologies and reconstruction algorithms are ever evolving, the datatypes that are used to store all the necessary data have to be able to evolve as well. This evolution has to happen in a way that grants access to data that has been written with previous versions. Hence, schema evolution is a crucial feature for podio generated EDMs.

A general schema evolution mechanism is highly non-trivial to implement since the problem space that needs to be covered is almost unbounded. Rather than trying to tackle this challenge, podio focuses on providing the necessary hooks to do schema evolution, and to be able to leverage existing schema evolution capabilities of existing I/O backends. With the hooks in place, the actually supported schema evolutions will be implemented as the use cases arise in the communities that use podio. For these implementations the goal is to have automatic code generation for as many cases as possible, but to still have the possibility for user defined evolution functions where necessary.

As a first piece of the solution we have implemented a tool that reads the high level yaml format definition of the same EDM in two different schema versions to produce a list of differences between the two. An example result of this tool is shown in Listing 1. As can be seen from the result the tool is able to categorize the detected schema changes into supported and (currently) unsupported schema changes. At this point in time this categorization targets the ROOT backend and its builtin schema evolution capabilities. An important aspect of this pre-processing step of running the comparison tool is that it allows one to check beforehand whether a given schema change is currently supported. Without this check it would be easily possible to lose access to already written data.

The next step for supporting schema evolution also for other backends than ROOT is to put the necessary schema evolution hooks into place. Fig. 2 shows where we plan to place these hooks within the Frame method for retrieving a collection. In this concept the schema evolution hooks are placed at the earliest point in time where they can possibly be; immediately after getting the POD buffers from the internal Frame data. In case an I/O backend has already performed schema evolution on these buffers, the hook essentially becomes a no-op function call, otherwise the hook will make sure to call the correct evolution function, depending on the requested collection type and involved schema versions. As a consequence of this placement of the schema evolution hook, users will only ever see the datatypes in their latest version.

Comparing datamodel versions v2 and v1

Found 4 schema changes:

- 'ToBeDroppedStruct' has been dropped
- 'ex2::NamespaceStruct' has an added member 'y'
- 'ex2::NamespaceStruct' has a dropped member 'y_old'
- 'ExampleStruct.x' changed type from int to double

Warnings:

- Definition 'ex2::NamespaceStruct' has a potential member rename 'y_old' -> 'y' of type 'int'.

ERRORS:

- Forbidden schema change in 'ex2::NamespaceStruct' for 'x' from 'std::array<int, 2>' to 'int'

Listing 1: Example result of the analysis of two datamodel definitions with different schema versions.

Figure 2. Conceptual implementation of getting a collection from a Frame, including reading the POD buffers from the internal Frame data and a potential evolution of these buffers (red) before the construction of a collection.

The last step towards full schema evolution support in podio generated EDMs is the automatic code generation from the list of differences between two schema versions. Here we have the basics in place with the comparison tool, and plan to implement a prototype shortly.

4. Other recent developments

Apart from these bigger developments that have just been described, there also have been some smaller improvements, that were triggered by different communities that are using podio.

JSON output The Phoenix event display framework [11] expects the event data that should be displayed to be in JSON format. In order to support this use case the possibility to dump collections of podio generated EDMs to JSON has recently been implemented using the *nlohmann/json* library [12]. We would like to point out that there are no plans to also support reading from JSON format in podio, and this is considered purely an output format.

Datamodel extensions In many future collider contexts the contents and necessary relations for datatypes that should represent the measured data of novel detector concepts are not yet established and some prototyping is necessary. To facilitate this prototyping phase we have recently implemented the possibility to extend existing datamodel definitions with new datatypes. By specifying an *upstream datamodel*, the datatypes and components defined in this upstream model become available for use in the datamodel extension. This is currently used by several detector concepts that extend the existing EDM4hep definition in order to develop novel reconstruction algorithms. By installing the high level yaml description file alongside the

build artifacts EDM4hep endorses this approach for prototyping. As we have already done so in other places [6] we would like to point out again, that this feature should be used solely for prototyping.

Another accomplishment that is made possible by this extension mechanism is the usage of EDM4hep types in EDM4eic [13], the datamodel used by the Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) community. The previous practice of re-defining the same datatypes again has now been replaced by the extension mechanism making this dependency much clearer. However, also in this use case the long term goal is to eventually converge on one set of datatypes defined in EDM4hep.

5. Conclusion & Outlook

The podio EDM toolkit has received crucial new developments recently; The Frame concept should allow for better usability in multi-threaded contexts, but also for a clearer separation of concerns with respect to I/O operations. Another longstanding issue is addressed by the implementation of schema evolution capabilities for generated EDMs. Here we have laid important ground work and have some clear steps ahead to get this feature fully functional. Additionally, there have been some smaller developments, mostly inspired by use cases from the communities using podio.

The next steps for podio are to finish schema evolution capabilities, as well as the integration of Frame based I/O functionality into more Key4hep components. We plan to release a first stable version of podio once all the necessary hooks for schema evolution are in place.

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